

THE USE OF VOCABULARY IN DIFFERENT TYPES OF SPEECH IN ENGLISH CLASSES

Considered in the article are various methods and techniques of using foreign vocabulary in speech. It is noted that the leading method in teaching a foreign language in a higher educational institution should be the communicative method.

The objective of the work is to study methods and techniques for the formation of productive lexical skills in foreign language classes in higher educational institutions.

The research methodology includes the method of analysis and synthesis of advanced pedagogical experience, analysis of literary sources, the method of comparison of various techniques and teaching methods effectiveness.

Scientific novelty consists in the fact that the experience of using different methods and techniques of mastering active foreign vocabulary is summarized, techniques of work in the classroom during the study of topics related to the students' future professional activities are suggested.

Conclusion. *If the purpose is to master active vocabulary, the most important premise of teaching a foreign language should be the creation of conditions for communication in the classroom, modeling real life in a learning space. The communicative teaching method is a universal method that allows teaching in the conditions close to a real diversity of communication spheres. The highest level of skills acquisition is the ability to use them in a new environment, in non-standard situations. Successful transfer of learning skills is provided only if the conditions for their formation are similar to the conditions of their functioning.*

The use of communicative games, discussion of problem situations and challenging issues in the classroom is a powerful motivator when learning a foreign language. They encourage students to turn to their personal experience, to find the necessary means for expressing thoughts, to apply their knowledge in non-standard situations.

Key words: *communicative teaching method, productive lexical skills, communicative games, lexical item, discussion of problem situations.*

Vocabulary is one of the most diverse and dynamic aspects of language and speech. The possibility of infinite variation in the meanings and uses of words complicates the process of mastering vocabulary and requires the search for new optimal ways to replenish the vocabulary.

In the current context, active vocabulary skills are of particular importance. The rapid pace of globalization requires effective intercultural communication. And the inclusion of a person in communication is unthinkable without mastering the means of communication. Mutual understanding is possible only when people speak the same language, which involves not only knowledge of lexical items, but also the ability to use them to master the totality of foreign language culture.

It is necessary to focus, first of all, on the final result when choosing teaching methods and techniques, and, in accordance with it, build the strategy of the educational process. If the purpose is to master active vocabulary, it is very important to create conditions for communication in the classroom, to model real life in a learning space. The communicative teaching method is a universal method that allows teaching in the conditions close to real diversity of communication spheres. The highest level of skills acquisition is the ability to use them in new conditions, in non-standard situations. Successful transfer of learning skills is provided only if the conditions for their formation are adequate for the conditions of their functioning.

The communicative method was developed in the 1960 – 1970s. Its fundamental theoretical foundation was grounded in the works of such famous scientists as E. I. Passov, G. A. Kitaygorodskaya, A. A. Leontiev and others.

This method is based on the idea that the personality is the subject and embodiment of the system of social relations. The driving force behind the formation and development of personality is the need for communication. At the same time, the person finds him / herself in the space of interindividual relations. In this regard, the ultimate goal is not to study the language as a system (the totality of lexical, phonetic and so on units and rules for their use), but to master speech skills, which serve as a means of communication and, ultimately, personality formation. The language performs the function of a universal classifying system and acquires significance only within the framework of the main purpose of the language as a means of communication, storage and transmission of information. A word is not a ready-to-use form to express thoughts. A thought is generated by the tension of the communicative task, clear speech perspective.

The objective of the work is to study methods and techniques for the formation of productive lexical skills in foreign language classes in higher educational institutions. The innovation consists in the fact that the experience of using different methods and techniques of mastering active foreign vocabulary is summarized, techniques of work in the classroom during the study of topics related to the students' future professional activities are suggested.

The use of vocabulary in various types of speech involves the use of learned vocabulary in independent statements, in new conditions. Speech abilities appear here in a new quality, in the form of skills. The skills are based on the knowledge of lexical items and the rules for their use, as well as on the handling of these items. One of the main characteristics of a skill is its stability in changing situations, and dynamism.

The interaction in educational environment becomes really communicative only when the speaker chooses what to say and how to do it [3, 132]. On the way to communicative interaction, the stages of controlled, prepared and unprepared speech are distinguished.

At the first stage, the teacher plays a great role in preparing for the utterance: he determines the form (means of expression) and the content of the utterance. The tasks at this stage have much in common with transformational exercises, for example: «*Retell the dialogue as a monolog based on keywords, add details and your own assessments*».

The prepared speech implies certain freedom either in the choice of means for expressing thoughts, or in determining the content of the statement: «*Make up questions to the movie and prepare the answers to them*», «*Expand the theses into the statement on a specific topic*», «*Give examples of statements with these words and phrases, describe the relevant situations*».

The highest level of speech abilities development is independence in the choice of both form and content.

The best conditions for the creative application of acquired knowledge and skills are created during communicative games and discussion of problem situations.

Communicative games can be used at all stages of the formation of active skills, from controlled to unprepared speech. Communicative games provide the opportunity for real communication, albeit within artificially defined boundaries. There are 8 areas of oral communication, in accordance with which it is necessary to form speech skills:

- 1) service (social and communicative roles of a customer, passenger, patient, subscriber, etc.);
- 2) family (social and communicative roles of a father, mother, son, daughter, etc.);
- 3) professional (the roles of a leader, subordinate, student, colleague, employee, etc.);
- 4) socio-cultural (the roles of an acquaintance, a friend, companion, etc.);
- 5) social activities (the roles of a member of a public organization, a correspondent, etc.);
- 6) administrative and legal (the roles of a visitor of a state institution, applicant, claimant, etc.);
- 7) games and hobbies (the roles of a collector, gardener, fisherman, animal lover, etc.);
- 8) entertainment (the roles of a spectator in a theatre, circus, a television viewer, etc.).

Role-playing and business games can be used when learning a foreign language in real-life communicative situations.

A student receives a certain role in a role-playing game and must behave in accordance with it. The role-playing game is a type of group educational activity aimed at reproduction of real practical activity of people based on role cards or a script. The description of a role can be given in a role card, and it is possible to present detailed information: there can be information about the person (kind, honest, lazy, and so on), about their life and speech experience, about habits, hobbies, and the like. However, the information should not be set out in too much detail, since the participant is deprived of creativity in this case. The description can also be brief so that the student can conceive the image of the character whose role s/he will play. Thus, each participant in a role-playing game performs speech actions due to the situation of communication, but has certain freedom of actions.

The role play carries an element of surprise, spontaneity and involves a spontaneous response. It is the element of surprise and unpreparedness, unpredictability of the situation. A role-playing game based on solving the problem ensures maximal communicative activity of students. The role play involves conscious and voluntary performance of the role and its subsequent discussion in the group.

In business games students can express their own thoughts, play themselves in the given conditions, in a certain situation, simulating the real one. The educational business game provides increasing proficiency with a foreign language as a means of professional communication. A business game has peculiarities unique for this type of academic work, without which the game cannot be considered as business: modeling close to real conditions of professional activity; the presence of conflict situations; obligatory joint activity of the game

participants. The preparatory phase of this form of work is to identify the main areas of students' professional interests.

One of the advantages of a business game is the two-pronged principle of gaming educational activities. On the one hand, a business game solves the «serious» tasks of developing the personality of a specialist, the students master the skills of team-building at work, the skills of professional communication and managing. On the other hand, this activity is implemented in a playful (partially gambling) form, which allows students to «liberate» themselves intellectually and emotionally, and to take creative initiative. Business games can be of the following types:

1) the analysis of specific professional situations – students get acquainted with the situation with a set of interrelated facts and phenomena that characterize this event. Then the students offer their solutions in a particular situation, which are discussed in a collective manner.

There is a detailed description of this type of work in linguistic literature (the case study method [2]), but it is carried out not in the form of a game, but in the form of a written analysis with subsequent discussion. Students are offered a detailed description of real-life situations borrowed from professional practice in various fields of activity. Having studied the conditions and facts, students should analyze what is the cause of the problem, what advantages and disadvantages can be found in the fact of the occurrence of this problem, and they should also offer and justify the way(s) to solve it.

2) role-playing – students receive initial data on the situation, and then play certain roles. For example, behavior in a conflict situation can depend on the position of an applicant, accuser, and so on. The roles are played in the presence of other students, who evaluate the actions of the participants in the situation, choose the optimal course of action in these conditions.

There are some examples of games that are appropriate to use in class with students. During the business game «Job Search» the group is divided into two parts: representatives of the employing organization and applicants for the vacancy. There is one vacancy, and applicants need to be able to present themselves properly, describe work experience, and so on. It is recommended that the information should be correlated with the following points that are necessary when filling out a resume:

- education (+ knowledge of languages, computer skills, driver's license);
- experience (post, functions);
- expected salary;
- raising the level of one's skills.

The representatives of the employing organization choose one of the applicants and give reasons for their choice.

A speech task can be built on the differences in the information available for students, in beliefs and attitudes, and so on. In accordance with this, distinguished are the games based on differences in pictures (picture gap), in texts (text gap), in beliefs (belief / opinion gap), and in evidence (reasoning gap) [1, 18].

The statements of such type of speech as description, are trained in the games based on picture gaps. For example, two participants are given similar pictures. They should find the differences based on their description without showing the pictures to each other. There may be some variants of this game: all the players receive cards, and, without showing them to each other, by description only, they try to match the pairs of identical cards (game «Twins»). The game «Another Age» is also interesting in terms of teaching the methods of description: the players are invited to imagine themselves to turn younger or older and tell the others about themselves taking into account the age characteristics.

To learn the techniques of description, a teacher can use the game «If I were (a journalist, a teacher, and so on)» – what qualities I would possess, what I would do, how I would spend my spare time, what I would spend my money on, how I would dress, etc.

To develop the skills of monologic speech, the skills of argumentation, in particular, a teacher can offer each student to evaluate which profession would be the most suitable for his / her classmates. They have to ground their conclusions, considering the personal qualities of each classmate. This technique is advisable to use only in a friendly team.

The example of a belief / opinion gap, when students have different beliefs and it is necessary to reach consensus, can be the game «Optimists and pessimists». The participants from the team of optimists make positive statements on a given topic, and pessimists should object to them. Then the teams develop a common understanding.

The reasoning gap assumes that students have different proofs that need to be gathered together and compared. The example can be «The most important problem game»: each group selects the card with the description of a problem. Their task is to prove that their problem is the most important for humanity. Then the jury decides upon which of the groups have managed to bring the most convincing proofs.

For the development of argumentation skills, the ability to defend one's opinion, technique of ranking activities is also interesting [4, 95]. This is sorting out the phenomena in ascending or descending order according to their importance and/or significance for students. It is important to justify one's choice. For example, personal,

professional qualities can be ranked. An application of this technique is ranking the qualities which are necessary for a particular profession. Each student should number them in the order of importance, based on the profession that he would like to acquire. There is a variant of this game, when a student is working independently and then his / her decision is being discussed in pairs or small groups best suited for this work. The list of personal qualities for ranking: *industrious, balanced, serious, polite, reasonable, disciplined, imaginative, creative, determined, self-confident, honest, witty, sociable, tactful, attractive, lively, ambitious.*

It is also possible to suggest answering the question «*What profession is the most creative (responsible, unusual, stressful, prestigious, popular)?*» And then rank the professions according to one of these characteristics.

One of the most effective ways to create conditions for communication is discussing some problem situations or burning issues. The themes for discussion may include:

- actual public events;
- a concept in which everyone puts personal meaning (*kindness, strengths and weaknesses of character, and so on*);
- controversial statement (*why read books if you have a TV or a computer*);
- an action (it is supposed to evaluate it from the point of view of morality);
- abnormal behavior that affects the others, and so on.

Students comment on the events, express their own opinions and attitudes to some particular fact.

It is also possible to discuss with students the proverbs and controversial statements related to money:

A good name is better than riches.

Having a lot of money makes you free.

All the millionaires are miserable people.

Money can buy everything.

A great fortune is a great slavery.

The discussion of problem situations or challenging issues can be held in non-traditional forms. For example, non-traditional lessons include a lesson-dispute, lesson-press conference, round table talk, etc. Changing the forms of work in the lesson stirs students' interest and motivates communication, which allows them to intensify their activities and corresponds to the principle of novelty. At the same time, improvement and final formation of the acquired lexical skills is achieved by recapitulation of the vocabulary. The unconventional approach to the lesson fosters students' independent creativity, reveals latent capacities. It is considered methodologically correct not to grade such forms of work, so that students should not feel scared of making mistakes. This liberates students and enables self-expression through spoken language.

The problem method of teaching foreign languages can also be effective. It implies active independent activity of students to resolve problem situations created under the guidance of a teacher. The highest level of practical implementation of the problem method is the situation when the student himself defines the problem and solves it. This prepares students for future independent life, teaches them to set realistic objectives and achieve their realization.

The development and improvement of verbal skills involves communication in the situations that simulate real ones, as well as a discussion of challenging issues. The need to find the means for expressing thoughts is highlighted. That is, communicative games, and discussions are a powerful motivating force when learning a foreign language.

References

1. Мильруд Р. П. Современные концептуальные принципы коммуникативного обучения иностранным языкам. *Иностранные языки в школе*. 2000. № 5. С. 17–22.
Milrud, R. P. (2000). *Sovremennye konceptualnye principy kommunikativnogo obucheniya inostrannym yazykam* [Modern conceptual principles of communicative teaching of foreign languages]. *Inostrannye yazyki v shkole. Foreign languages at school*, No. 5.
2. Dow Anne, R., Ryan Joseph, T. (1994). *Interactive language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 210 p.
3. Larsen-Freeman, D. (1986). *Techniques and principles in language teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 142 p.
4. Nolasco, R., Lois, A. (1995). *Conversation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1995. 148 p.

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ФОРМУВАННЯ РЕПРОДУКТИВНИХ ЛЕКСИЧНИХ НАВИЧОК НА ЗАНЯТТЯХ З ІНОЗЕМНОЇ МОВИ У ВИЩІ

У статті розглядаються різні методи і прийоми використання іношомовної лексики в мовленні. Підкреслюється, що провідним методом навчання іноземної мови у закладах вищої освіти має бути комунікативний метод.

Метою роботи є вивчення методів і прийомів формування репродуктивних лексичних навичок на заняттях з іноземної мови у закладах вищої освіти.

Методологія дослідження включає метод аналізу та узагальнення передового педагогічного досвіду, аналізу літературних джерел, порівняння ефективності різних методів і прийомів навчання.

Наукова новизна полягає в тому, що узагальнено досвід використання різних методів і прийомів засвоєння іношомовної активної лексики, запропоновано прийоми роботи на практичних заняттях під час вивчення тем, пов'язаних з майбутньою професійною діяльністю студентів.

Висновки. Оволодіння активною лексикою з комунікативною метою передбачає створення умов для спілкування в аудиторії, моделювання реального життя в навчальному процесі. Комунікативний метод навчання – це універсальний метод, який дозволяє навчати в умовах, близьких до реального розмаїття сфер спілкування. Найвищий рівень набуття навичок – це здатність використовувати їх у нових умовах, в нестандартних ситуаціях. Успішне перенесення навичок у нові ситуації забезпечується тільки в тому випадку, коли умови їх формування подібні умовам їх функціонування.

Використання комунікативних ігор, обговорення проблемних ситуацій на заняттях є потужним мотивуючим фактором при вивченні іноземної мови. Вони спонукають студентів звертатися до свого особистого досвіду, знаходити необхідні засоби для висловлення думок, застосовувати свої знання в нестандартних ситуаціях.

Ключові слова: комунікативний метод навчання, продуктивні лексичні навички, комунікативні ігри, лексична одиниця, проблемні ситуації.

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